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A STUDY ON THE INVESTORS' PREFERENCE TOWARDS VARIOUS INVESTMENT AVENUES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO GENDER

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ABSTRACT

The advent and evolution of behavioral finance has brought with it a revolution in the finance industry. Investors do not act rationally in taking decisions relating to investment. They have certain weaknesses like cognitive and emotional which take a predominating role in taking investment decision of individuals. They have behavioral biases in the event of taking investment decision. They simply react to the information available with them and accordingly react to the environment. There are lots of investment alternatives where investor can invest such as Gold, silver, real estate, bank deposits, PPF, shares, derivatives, etc. Several number of studies have conclude that women invest their asset portfolios more unadventurously than their male counterparts, a finding that is generally consistent with the "common wisdom" of financial services providers. The present paper tries to find out the perception of male and female investors regarding various variables while investing in different alternatives. The paper tries to study the attitude of male and female investors towards different investment avenues. The researchers have selected 60 male investors and 40 female investors from Moradabad region. The study uses independent t-test, mean scores to test the hypothesis. The paper concludes that investors whether male or female should look in all avenues while investing their funds. Some investments are risky and some are not, so as per the age of investors they should decide about risky or less risky investments.

KEYWORDS: Risk, financial products, investment alternatives, financial planning.

INTRODUCTION

During the last two decades, a new field known as behavioral finance began to emerge in many academic journals, business publications, and even local newspapers. Behavioral Finance as a field of study is not new in fact the foundations of behavioral finance can be traced back over 150 years. One of the first published written evidences can be found in MacKay's "Delusions and the Madness of Crowds" published in 1841 which presents a chronological timeline of the various panics and schemes throughout history. This work shows how group behavior applies to the financial markets of today. Selden's 1912 book "Psychology of the Stock Market" was one of the first to apply the field of psychology directly to the stock market. This classic discusses the emotional and psychological forces at work on investors and traders in the financial markets. Behavioural finance attempts to explain and increase understanding of the reasoning patterns of investors, including the emotional processes involved and the degree to which they influence the decision-making process.

The various interdisciplinary fields which have contributed or have been the foundation pillars in the development of behavioural finance are:

- **FINANCE:** Finance is the discipline which is concerned with the acquisition, allocation and management of financial resources.
- **PSYCHOLOGY:** Psychology is the discipline which studies the behaviour and the mental process of the subject under study and how these process are affected by individuals' mental, physical state and external environment.
- **SOCIOLOGY:** Sociology is the discipline which studies the human social behavior and groups. The field focuses on how the individuals' social relationships affects its attitudes and behavior.

VARIOUS INVESTMENT ALTERNATIVES

There are lots of investment alternatives available to investors depending upon their criteria. The important ones are mentioned herein below:

- Gold/Silver
- Shares
- Bonds/Debentures
- Derivatives
- Mutual Funds
- Bank fixed deposits
- Post Office Savings (MIS, NSC)

- Insurance
- Public Provident Fund
- Real Estate

GENDER AND INVESTORS BEHAVIOUR

Several number of studies have conclude that women invest their asset portfolios more unadventurously than their male counterparts, a finding that is generally consistent with the “common wisdom” of financial services providers. The state of the art of the literature suggests that indeed women tend to hold less risky portfolios than men. These findings are often explained by the perception that women have a stronger aversion to risk because of their weaker economic and social position, which in turn implies their exposure to other sources of risk, such as labor risk, in addition to those associated with their asset holdings. The general finding in the literature is that women choose less risky portfolios than men which suggest that women have a stronger aversion against taking on financial risk. Jianakoplos and Bernasek (1998) in their study concluded that single women exhibit relatively more risk aversion in financial decision making than single men. Prior research on gender and risk aversion shows mixed results. There are many sources that show females to be more risk averse, but since the 1980s there have been many studies done that show females take similar risks as males. Thus the resultant investment choices between the female and their male counterparts tend to vary. Men tend to have more riskier investment avenues in their portfolio as compared to women who keep a relative measure of their investment choices by investing in much safer investment alternatives.

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Grable and Lytton (1999) examine whether demographic factors would be good predictors of financial tolerance based on a university survey from 1997 that includes both faculty and staff. Grable and Lytton highlight the role of financial education in determining risk taking, with the more financially educated participants more likely to take risk (Grable & Lytton, 1999). Bajtelsmit and Bernasek summarize the literature that explored risk taking differences between men and women, attempting to reach a consensus on why women invest differently. They find that the literature supports the argument, both through experiments and field data, that women make more conservative decisions than men and that they make more conservative decisions with respect to investments (Bajtelsmit & Bernasek, 1996). Hinz, McCarthy and Turner find that the female effect persists after demographic controls showing that men are more likely to invest in risky assets (Hinz, McCarthy, & Turner, 1997). Not only is the level of human capital important for investment decisions, but also the correlation. Fortunately, company stock is not an option for FRS participants, so correlation issues between the expected returns and expected income should be minimal. The difference in investment preference across genders has received much attention. The responsibility for the difference has been placed on both men and women by the research. Most of the research reports that women invest more conservatively than men (Bajtelsmit & VanDerhei, 1997; Croson & Gneezy, 2009). But the reasons for the differences are more diverse. The potential for overconfidence in the valuation of securities may push men to choose riskier strategies or make them more likely to rebalance away from default investments.

On the other side of the gender argument, Croson and Gneezy summarize the research covering gender differences in investments and argue that it is women's level of risk aversion that pushes them to choose the less risky portfolios (Croson & Gneezy, 2009). Volpe et al. (1996) assessed the knowledge of personal investment among 454 college students and the relationship between investment literacy level and gender, academic discipline and experience. They used exam type questionnaire that covered variety of personal investment topics including risk, diversification, financial advisor, tax planning, stock market valuation, business mathematics, bond and mutual fund performance, global investing and interest rate. The results indicated that in general college students were illiterate about personal investment specifically in the topics about global investing, stock market valuation, impact of interest rate changes and tax planning. The results demonstrated that female students were significantly less knowledgeable about personal investing than male students specifically in the areas of stock valuation, mutual fund performance, business mathematics and global investing. Control is the key factor of investor behavior. Many behavior researchers found the relationship between individual investor behavior and control. Individual investors that trade quickly and watch their investment carefully they have high level control about their investment decision. Investor involvement and control increase the confidence and choice of investor behavior (Langer and Roth, 1975). Rayan and Zaichkowsky (2010) found that there is a significant relationship between investor behavior and their investment control.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The present paper aims at the following objectives:

- To know about the perception of male and female investors regarding various variables while investing in different alternatives.
- To study the attitude of male and female investors towards different investment avenues

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Type	: Empirical
Type of Sampling	: Convenience Sampling
Sampling Unit	: Individual persons
Sampling Universe	: Region Moradabad, Uttar Pradesh
Sample size	: 100 (Male 60, Female 40)
Data Type	: Primary as well as Secondary Data
Data Source	: Survey through questionnaire
Tools	: Independent T-test and mean scores have been taken for the data taken on a five point likert scale.

Scope of the study : The scope of study is related to persons in different occupations and having different levels of income in region Moradabad (Uttar Pradesh). The scope of the research shall be in reliance with the methods and instruments of research used in this study. Special attention has been given to carry out the research in a manner such that it contributes to the overall study of use of behavioural finance. Opinion of various experts in Moradabad city of Uttar Pradesh has been taken about the trend towards investment. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on behavioural finance.

HYPOTHESIS

Researchers have framed nine hypothesis. The details are mentioned herein below:

HYPOTHESIS 1

H_{1o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Safety of Principle of Investment amount

H_{1a}: There is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Safety of Principle of Investment amount

HYPOTHESIS 2

H_{2o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Liquidity in Investment

H_{2a}: There is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Liquidity in Investment

HYPOTHESIS 3

H_{3o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Capital Appreciation

H_{3a}: There is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Capital Appreciation

HYPOTHESIS 4

H_{4o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Regular Income

H_{4a}: There is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Regular Income from their investments

HYPOTHESIS 5

H_{5o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Return on Investment

H_{5a}: There is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Return on Investment

HYPOTHESIS 6

H_{6o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Tax Savings from Investments

H_{6a}: There is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Tax Savings from Investments

HYPOTHESIS 7

H_{7o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Serving future financial needs/Securing future

H_{7a}: There is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Serving future financial needs/Securing future

HYPOTHESIS 8

H_{8o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Easy accessibility in Market/Marketability

H_{8a}: There is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Easy accessibility in Market/Marketability

HYPOTHESIS 9

H_{9o}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Protection against Inflation

H_{9a}: There is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding Protection against Inflation

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

(A) GENERAL DETAILS

Questions were asked from the respondents about their perceptions regarding various variables relating to investment. We get the following data:

TABLE 1: GENERAL DETAILS OF RESPONDENTS MAKING INVESTMENTS IN DIFFERENT ALTERNATIVES

S. No.	Variables	Responses	Male	Female	Total
1	Gender		60	40	100
2	Age (In Years)	18 – 25	8	5	13
		26 – 35	15	9	24
		36 – 50	15	12	27
		51 – 60	12	9	21
		Above 60	10	5	15
3	Marital Status	Married	45	25	70
		Unmarried	15	15	30
4	Occupation	Business	21	8	29
		Service	14	20	34
		Professional	10	10	20
		Farmer	7	0	7
		Student	8	2	10
5	Area of Residence	Rural	20	10	30
		Urban	40	30	70
6	Income Level	< 100000	10	5	15
		100000-300000	12	8	20
		300000-500000	26	16	42
		500000-1000000	10	10	20
		> 1000000	2	1	3
7	Investments Made	< 25000	10	5	15
		25000-50000	10	11	21
		50000-75000	2	4	6
		75000-100000	1	4	5
		100000-200000	35	15	50
		> 200000	2	1	3

TABLE 2: AVERAGE INVESTMENT HOLDINGS (IN PERCENTAGE) IN DIFFERENCE INVESTMENT ALTERNATIVES

Investment Alternative	Gold/Silver	Shares	Bonds	Derivatives	Mutual Funds	Bank FD	Post Office Savings Schemes	LI C	PP F	Real estate	Total
Average Percentage of Investment											100 %
Male	15	17	3	5	8	10	7	8	10	17	100
Female	30	5	2	1	2	30	10	5	10	5	100

(B) TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

TABLE 3: MEAN OF PERCEPTIONS OF MALE AND FEMALE INVESTORS

S. No.	Variables	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1	Safety of Principle Investment Amount	Male	60	4.27	.710	.092
		Female	40	4.40	.632	.100
2	Liquidity in Investment	Male	60	3.18	.873	.113
		Female	40	3.28	.784	.124
3	Capital Appreciation	Male	60	3.25	.795	.103
		Female	40	3.18	.903	.143
4	Regular Income	Male	60	2.30	.462	.060
		Female	40	3.80	.608	.096
5	Return on Investment	Male	60	4.37	.663	.086
		Female	40	4.23	.423	.067
6	Tax Savings	Male	60	3.07	.880	.114
		Female	40	1.80	1.137	.180
7	Serving Future Financial Needs/Securing future	Male	60	3.65	.685	.088
		Female	40	3.38	.628	.099
8	Easy accessibility in market/Marketability	Male	60	3.27	.800	.103
		Female	40	2.55	.846	.134
9	Protection against inflation	Male	60	3.22	.783	.101
		Female	40	2.28	1.261	.199

TABLE 4: INDEPENDENT SAMPLES TEST

Variables		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Safety of Principle investment amount	Equal variances assumed	.400	.528	-.960	98	.339	-.133	.139	-.409	.142
	Equal variances not assumed			-.983	90.039	.328	-.133	.136	-.403	.136
Liquidity in investment	Equal variances assumed	.431	.513	-.535	98	.594	-.092	.171	-.431	.248
	Equal variances not assumed			-.547	89.644	.586	-.092	.168	-.425	.241
Capital Appreciation	Equal varia	1.064	.305	.438	98	.662	.075	.171	-.26	.415

	nces assu med								5	
	Equal varia nces not assu med			.42 7	76. 252	.67 1	.075	.176	- .27 5	.42 5
Regular Income	Equal varia nces assu med	.75 4	.3 87	- 14. 000	98	.00 0	-1.500	.107	- 1.7 13	- 1.2 87
	Equal varia nces not assu med			- 13. 263	68. 175	.00 0	-1.500	.113	- 1.7 26	- 1.2 74
Return on investment	Equal varia nces assu med	19. 517	.0 00	1.1 98	98	.23 4	.142	.118	- .09 3	.37 6
	Equal varia nces not assu med			1.3 04	97. 853	.19 5	.142	.109	- .07 4	.35 7
Tax savings	Equal varia nces assu med	3.0 18	.0 85	6.2 65	98	.00 0	1.267	.202	.86 5	1.6 68
	Equal varia nces			5.9 56	69. 121	.00 0	1.267	.213	.84 2	1.6 91

	not assumed									
Serving future financial needs/Securing future	Equal variances assumed	.308	.580	2.033	98	.045	.275	.135	.007	.543
	Equal variances not assumed			2.069	88.548	.041	.275	.133	.011	.539
Easy accessibility in market/Marketability	Equal variances assumed	.185	.668	4.290	98	.000	.717	.167	.385	1.048
	Equal variances not assumed			4.242	80.451	.000	.717	.169	.380	1.053
Protection against inflation	Equal variances assumed	26.932	.000	4.609	98	.000	.942	.204	.536	1.347
	Equal variances not assumed			4.213	59.065	.000	.942	.223	.494	1.389

The researchers have used dependent t test, mean scores, pearson correlation to test the above stated hypothesis.

HYPOTHESIS 1

On average, male respondents have almost similar concern about the safety of their principal amount ($M = 4.27$, $SE = 0.092$) as female respondents ($M = 4.40$, $SE = 0.100$), $t(99) = -0.960$, $p > .05$ Null Hypothesis is accepted and alternate hypothesis is rejected. We can conclude that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding safety of principle of investment amount. Both type of respondents care for the safety of their investments.

HYPOTHESIS 2

On average, male respondents have almost similar concern about the liquidity in their investments ($M = 3.18$, $SE = 0.113$) as female respondents ($M = 3.28$, $SE = 0.124$), $t(99) = -0.535$, $p > .05$ Null Hypothesis is accepted and alternate hypothesis is rejected. We can conclude that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding liquidity in their investments. Both types of respondents want liquidity in their investments.

HYPOTHESIS 3

On average, male respondents have almost similar concern about the capital appreciation ($M = 3.25$, $SE = 0.103$) as female respondents ($M = 3.18$, $SE = 0.143$), $t(99) = 0.438$, $p > .05$ Null Hypothesis is accepted and alternate hypothesis is rejected. We can conclude that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding capital appreciation. Both types of respondents want appreciation in their investments.

HYPOTHESIS 4

On average, male respondents are less concern about the regular income on their investments ($M = 2.30$, $SE = 0.060$) as compared to female respondents ($M = 3.80$, $SE = 0.096$), $t(99) = 14$, $p < .05$ Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. We can conclude that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding regular income on their investments.

HYPOTHESIS 5

On average, male respondents have almost similar concern about the return on investment ($M = 4.37$, $SE = 0.086$) as female respondents ($M = 4.23$, $SE = 0.067$), $t(99) = 1.198$, $p > .05$ Null Hypothesis is accepted and alternate hypothesis is rejected. We can conclude that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding return on investment. Both types of respondents want good return on their investments.

HYPOTHESIS 6

On average, female respondents are less concern about the tax savings while investing their funds ($M = 1.80$, $SE = 0.180$) as compared to male respondents ($M = 3.07$, $SE = 0.114$), $t(99) = 14$, $p < .05$ Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. We can conclude that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding tax savings considerations while making investments.

HYPOTHESIS 7

On average, male respondents are more concern about the serving future financial needs from investments ($M = 3.65$, $SE = 0.088$) as compared to female respondents ($M = 3.38$, $SE = 0.099$), $t(99) = 2.033$, $p < .05$ Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. We can conclude that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding serving future financial needs from investments.

HYPOTHESIS 8

On average, male respondents are more concern about the easy accessibility in market (Marketability of their investments) ($M = 3.27$, $SE = 0.103$) as compared to female respondents ($M = 2.55$, $SE = 0.134$), $t(99) = 4.29$, $p < .05$ Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. We can conclude that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding easy accessibility in market (Marketability of their investments).

HYPOTHESIS 9

On average, male respondents are more concern about the protection from inflation of their investments ($M = 3.22$, $SE = 0.101$) as compared to female respondents ($M = 2.28$, $SE = 0.199$), $t(99) = 4.609$, $p < .05$ Null Hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. We can conclude that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female regarding protection from inflation of their investments.

FINDINGS

The findings of this study are mentioned herein below:

- 1) Both male and female investors care for the safety of their investments;
- 2) Both male and female investors want that in case of need or emergency their investments should be converted into cash without much loss of investment;
- 3) Everybody wants that his or her investments should grow with the passage of time. Same case we find in this study where both male and female investors want capital appreciation;
- 4) As regards regular income on the investment female respondents are more interested in getting regular income from their investments;

- 5) Both male and female investors want higher return on investments;
- 6) Male investors are more interested to save their income tax by investing in tax deductible alternatives such as PPF, LIC, tax saving Bank fixed deposits, etc.;
- 7) As male respondents have greater responsibilities to maintain their family, so they invest their funds in such a manner that it will help them in the education as well as marriage of their children. They want that their investments should serve the future requirements.
- 8) Male investors are more interested in investing in those type of investments which have access to easy market.
- 9) Male investors are more interested in investing in such areas which can protect them from inflation. They want that their investments should safeguard them from high inflation.

SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

Investors whether male or female, should look in all avenues while investing their funds in different assets. Some investments are risky and some are not, so as per the age of investors they should decide about risky or less risky investments. Older investors should avoid risky investments while younger generation investors can take risk. There are lots of considerations while investing such as tax planning, future needs, safety of investments, recurring income, etc. So as per the requirement of individual investor he or she should consider these variables.

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